

A Review of Synthesis of Aminoguanidine Derivatives and Some of their Biological Activities

Patil Tejal P.; Patil Pradhya Y.; Dr. Kakade Rajanikant T.

Abstract:- Five-ring scaffolds are the most important and best-known heterocycles and are an essential component of many natural products and drugs. These scaffolds are centrally located and are the main structures of many different drugs. These medications include antibiotics, antibiotics, antibiotics, antibiotics, antibiotics, antibiotics, and antibiotics. In this review, we will mainly talk about aminoguanidine bicarbonate derivatives due to their important medicinal properties. This is partly because, unlike other isomers, they are chemically stable and heat stable and can be used as bioisosteres in pharmaceutical production. We consider the modifications of different aminoguanidine bicarbonate derivatives, especially the anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer drugs published in the last 5 years, as an important research area. This article aims to provide an in-depth study and analysis of the latest developments in chemical aminoguanidine bicarbonate derivatives. This would be a good starting point for future research.

I. INTRODUCTION

Heterocycles are ring compounds that contain one or more different ring atoms. Five- and six-membered compounds are the most important heterocyclic systems. ¹Although they are heterocyclic compounds, the ring structure usually contains at least one carbon atom and one or more elements such as sulfur, oxygen, and nitrogen. Since it is generally thought that no carbon can be replaced by a carbon atom, they are called heteroatoms. This formula can be made from aromatic or non-aromatic rings.

Heterocyclic chemistry is a branch of chemistry that deals with compounds, products, reactions, and applications.²

Aminoguanidine bicarbonate has attracted recent attention due to its practical preparation and important physical properties. Aminoguanidine bicarbonate not only forms salts with carboxylic acids, but also condenses with acids under acidic conditions to form hydrazides.³ Aminoguanidine bicarbonate has been subjected to extensive studies in recent years. The aminoguanidine bicarbonate scaffold is very versatile and has been part of several clinically used drugs. They have found use as antitubercular, antimicrobial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and antiviral agents, particularly anti-HIV agents. Many reports have appeared in the literature highlighting their chemical and pharmacological uses.

This review emphasizes the various pharmacological properties associated with aminoguanidine bicarbonate derivatives. The review covers the progress made over the last ten years.

II. PREPARATION OF AMINOGUANIDINE DERIVATIVES

Several methods for synthesizing aminoguanidine bicarbonate derivatives are widely described in the literature. The various reported syntheses may be cyclization of aminoguanidine bicarbonate in a one-, two-, or three-step process.

A new route to the synthesis of 3-amino-5,6-di(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,2,4-triazine (1) was synthesized by an analogous route shown in Scheme 1. From refluxing 4,4'-difluoro benzyl with aminoguanidine bicarbonate in n-butanol and subjected to evaluation of their plant protection and antifungal activity.⁴

Scheme 1: 3-amino-5,6-di(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,2,4 triazine

A series of new 5-6 diphenyl-(1,2,4)triazine-3-amine (2) was synthesized in an analogous manner shown in Scheme 2. From refluxing benzyl with aminoguanidine

bicarbonate in n-butanol and subjected to evaluation of their anticonvulsant activity.⁵

Scheme 2: synthesis of 5-6 diphenyl-(1,2,4) triazine-3-amine

A new heterocyclic system 5-amino-1H 1,2,4-triazole-3-carboxylic acid (3) was synthesized by an analogous route shown in Scheme 3. They were synthesized by reacting

aminoguanidine bicarbonate with excess oxalic acid in the presence of a base and subjected to evaluation of their anticancer activity.⁶

Scheme 3: 5-amino-1H-1,2,4-triazole-3-carboxylic acid

A series of new n-amino tetrazoles (4) were synthesized by an analogous route shown in Scheme 4. The synthesis was based on Thiele's method, which involves the

interaction of aminoguanidine bicarbonate with nitric acid produced in situ from potassium nitrite and nitric acid and subjected to evaluation of their anticonvulsant activity.⁷

Scheme 4: n-aminotetrazole

A series of novel benzodiazepine-1,2,4 (benzo TAP-1,2,4) compounds were synthesized analogously to those shown in Scheme 5, reaction of the isotonic anhydride with aminoguanidine bicarbonate in AcOH to obtain the triazine (5) and further reaction of this with oxalyl chloride,

chloroacetyl chloride, 2-chloropropionyl chloride, 3-chloropropionyl chloride and malononitrile in dry benzene and anhydrous K₂CO₃ under reflux conditions at 6-10 and subjected to evaluation of their antitumor activity.⁸

Scheme 5: benzotriazepane-1,2,4 (benzoTAP- 1,2,4) compounds

A new series of **azidotriazole** compounds, **5-azido-1,2,4-triazolyl-5-acetic acid (ATAA) (11)** were synthesized based on the **Sandmeyer reaction**. They are produced by a similar method in Scheme 6. It is synthesized by intramolecular condensation of

malonic acid and aminoguanidine bicarbonate in an alkaline medium. In general, the oxidation reaction is carried out at 05°C, followed by diazotization in sodium nitrite and sulfuric acid at 0°C to give 5-amino-1,2,4-triazolyl-5-acetic acid, and after testing, with excess sodium azide at 50°C to evaluate its antibacterial activity.⁹

Scheme 6: 5-azido-1,2,4 triazolyl-5-acetic acid (ATAA)

One of the new amino-5,6-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazines (12) was synthesized by a method similar to that shown in Scheme 7 of cyclization condensation of the

benzyl group with aminoguanidine bicarbonate under reflux in n-butanol evaluated for HIV protection.¹⁰

Scheme 7: amino-5, 6-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazines

A series of new (E)-N-(1H-tetrazol-5-yl)-substituted amide (13), synthesis of 5-amino tetrazole was based on Thiele's method. Synthesized by the analog shown in Scheme 8, by diazotization in sodium nitrite, then the

synthesis of 5-acetyl tetrazole was achieved, the synthesis of (E)-N-(1H-tetrazole-5-yl)-substituted amide compound was subjected to evaluate their antifungal activity.¹¹

Scheme 8:(E)-N-(1H-tetrazol-5-yl)-substituted amide.

A series of novel 3-amino-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazin-6-ones (14) were synthesized analogously to those shown in Scheme 9. They are obtained from chloroacetyl chloride and aminoguanidine bicarbonate. Chloroacetylation takes place on the more basic atom N1, the resulting 1-chloroacetylaminoguanidine cyclizes to triazine as a result of a nucleophilic We cannot separate the nitrogen

atom from the amino group of the methylene carbon atom in the middle molecule. The reaction was carried out with high yield in glacial acetic acid, in the presence of sodium acetate as a cyclizing agent, in equimolar ratios of starters and at room temperature, and its antifungal activity was evaluated.¹²

Scheme 9: 3-Amino-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazin-6-on

A series of novel lamotrigine (16) was synthesized by an analogous route shown in Scheme 10. Which involves 2-(2,3-chlorophenyl)-2-(guanidin-yl-imino)acetonitrile (15)

Schiff base 2,3-dichloro benzoyl cyanide with aminoguanidine bicarbonate cyclization and subjected to evaluation of their anticonvulsant activity.¹³

Scheme 10: Lamotrigine

One of the new trinitromethyl-substituted monocyclic 5-nitro-3-trinitromethyl-1H-1,2,4-triazoles (19) was synthesized by a similar method to Scheme 11. The precursor 5-amino-1,2,4-triazole-3-ylacetic acid (17) was prepared using an aqueous solution of aminoguanidine bicarbonate and malonic acid and treated with an excess of nitrite ions. Made to form 5-nitro-1H-1,2,4-triazole-3-yl-acetic acid (18). Attempts to oxidize the

amino group to nitro using hydrogen peroxide and sodium tungstate were unsuccessful. Nitration of 5-nitro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-3-ylacetic acid using 100% HNO₃/96% H₂SO₄ gave 5-nitro-3-trinitromethyl-H-1 in good (75%) yield. 2,4-triazole (19), show high density, good thermal stability, an acceptable oxygen balance, excellent detonation properties, positive heat of formation, and are subject to evaluation of their energetic properties.

Scheme 11: tri-nitromethyl-substituted monocyclic 5-nitro-3-tri-nitromethyl-1H-1,2,4-triazole

A series of novel *N*-(1-(2-cyano-3-phenylacryloyl)-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)acetamide (21) was synthesized by an analogous route shown in Scheme 12. precursor 2-(2-cyano-3-substituted phenylacryloyl)hydrazinecarboximidamide (20) was

prepared using aminoguanidine bicarbonate, ethyl cyanoacetate, anhydrous potassium carbonate and an aromatic aldehyde. The reaction is carried out using ethyl orthoformate and the formation of compound (21) and subjected to evaluation of their anticancer activity.¹⁵

Scheme 12: *N*-(1-(2-Cyano-3-phenylacryloyl)-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)acetamide.

A series of novel pyrimidinylpyrazole (21) was synthesized by an analogous route shown in Scheme 13. It can be obtained by a stepwise reaction of aminoguanidine bicarbonate and a diketone compound. R₁, R₂ and R₃ are

determined depending on the intended pyrimidinylpyrazole compound. This reaction in the absence of solvent or reaction in water is subjected to evaluation of their antitumor activity.¹⁶

Scheme 13: pyrimidinylpyrazole

A new set of 1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-3-ylbenzenesulfonamide derivatives (24) was synthesized by a method similar to that shown in Scheme 14. The precursor 3-amino-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole (23) was obtained by cyclization condensation of aminoguanidine bicarbonate an

d a suitable carboxylic acid and was used directly in the next step. Nucleophilic substitution reaction of 3-amino-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole and sulfonyl chloride derivatives. Preparation of compound (24) and evaluation of its antibacterial activity.¹⁷

Scheme 14: 1H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl benzenesulfonamide derivatives

A series of new 5,7-dimethyl-1,2,4-triazolo[1,5a(14C)]pyrimidine-2-carbaldehyde (27) were synthesized analogously to those shown in Scheme 15. The precursor (5-amino-1H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)methanol (25) was obtained by cyclization of aminoguanidine bicarbonate and glycolic acid. The next step was directly reacted with

acetylacetone to give (5,7-dimethyl-[1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidin-2-yl)methanol (26), then PhI(OAc)₂/TEMPO mediated oxidation of compound (26) to prepare compound (27) and subjected to evaluation of their herbicidal activity and excellent fungicidal activity.¹⁸

Scheme 15: 5,7-dimethyl-1,2,4-triazolo[1,5a(14C)]pyrimidine-2-carbaldehyde

III. CONCLUSION

Aminoguanidine bicarbonate remains an interesting area for researchers, as evidenced by the latest work from 2023. Many of the aminoguanidine bicarbonate derivatives described in this review show potent biological activities and deserve more detailed research in this area. We hope that this article, which synthesizes the knowledge about the biological activities of aminoguanidine bicarbonate, will increase scientific interest in these compounds and encourage the development of new derivatives and their introduction into research in further studies.

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